

INCREASING PHYSICAL ACTIVITY IN CHILDREN WITH ASTHMA: A FAMILY AND COMMUNITY APPROACH

Linda Mendoza MSN, CPNP-PC, AE-C
Jean O'Neil, DNP, RN, FNP-BC -- Stacey A. Warner, PhD, RN, CPNP-PC

Background

- Asthma and obesity are prevalent among U.S. children, impacting 6.5% and 19.7% respectively, with significant health implications including increased symptoms and healthcare utilization
- Factors like parental concerns about asthma symptoms with exercise and inadequate physical activity options contribute to lower activity levels and increased obesity risk.
- Culturally appropriate family-centered interventions and community partnerships are recommended to address barriers to physical activity and reduce the risk of obesity in children with asthma, improving overall health outcomes

Problem Statement

Wellness on Wheels (WoW), a mobile clinic, serving underserved children with asthma, identified a significant increase in obesity rates among its patients, indicating a need to address obesity prevention with their families.

Purpose Statement

This project aimed to evaluate the effectiveness of a community-based, family-centered education program in improving knowledge about physical activity in children with asthma, with the objective of reducing obesity risk through heightened awareness and engagement.

Methods

Design: Pre-test/post-test survey
Setting: Community/Family Centers in Orange County, CA
Participants: Parents of children with asthma, ages 6 to 11, and are patients of WoW
Measurement Tools: A mix of open-ended and five-point Likert scale surveys
Intervention Plan: A 1-hour educational session via Power Point, in Spanish or English
Data Analysis: Descriptive/ Paired Wilcoxon Sum

Adapted Iowa Model Revised For Evidenced-Based Practice

Results

Sociodemographic Characteristics

Characteristics	N	%
Age		
25-34 years	1	12.5
35-44 years	5	62.5
45-54 years	2	25
Gender		
He	1	12.5
She	7	87.5
Them	0	
Ethnicity		
Hispanic or Latino	8	100
Non-Hispanic or Latino	0	
Race		
White	1	12.5
No response	2	25
Prefer not to state	5	62.5
Relationship to child		
Father	1	12.5
Mother	7	87.5
Family household #		
Four (4)	2	25
Five (5)	1	12.5
Six (6)	5	62.5

- All children are enrolled in Medi-Cal and live in underserved communities
- 8/9 participants completed all components of the surveys
- 1 parent participated in the English session/ 8 in the Spanish session

Pre-education: Asthma Symptoms and Physical Activity Characteristics

- 62.5% reported oral steroid usage within the last 12 months
- 75% reported that their child had trouble with their asthma during exercise
- 62.5% reported that their child utilized albuterol (for relief of symptoms) after exercise

Pre/Post Education: Knowledge, Perceptions, Beliefs, and Community Assessment

- No statistically significant differences were observed between pre- and post-intervention groups across survey components
- Perceptions changed related to "physical activity may make a child's asthma better," with 3 out of 8 participants (37.5%) changing from "undecided" pre-intervention to "agree" or "strongly agree" post-intervention
- Perceptions regarding "there is not enough time for physical activity" and "I am afraid that my child will get sick if he or she does physical activity" shifted from agreement to disagreement post-intervention

One Month Post- Survey

- Only one participant completed survey
- Parent reported that the child's physical activity goal was not met due to "not enough time"

Discussion

- History of oral steroid use and trouble with their asthma during exercise indicate poor asthma control in the participants' children, highlighting the need for tailored asthma management strategies
- Positive shifts in participants' perceptions post intervention, indicate increased understanding of the benefits of physical activity, which can potentially lead to reducing obesity risk
- Lack of time emerged as a barrier to physical activity

Implications

- Nurse practitioners play a crucial role in implementing family-centered interventions to address obesity in children with asthma
- Family and community partnerships are vital for sustaining tailored educational programs and overcoming barriers to physical activity in underserved communities

Limitations

- Limited sample size and tight project deadline
- Difficulty in recruiting participants
- Low participation potentially due to weekday sessions during school hours
- Incomplete or insufficient data resulting from incomplete surveys

Recommendations

- Use phone calls or community flyers to boost engagement in addition to emails
- Schedule sessions during evenings and weekends to improve accessibility
- Provide childcare or activities during sessions to ease caregiving responsibilities
- Offer online participation for transportation or attendance constraints

References

